

Urban Violence and Citizenship

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Political protest is the expression of the non-acquiescence about a decision or a set of political decisions, or the non-acknowledgement of the legitimacy for the decision making process. The political intervention is assumed to be, in that case, extremely relevant for the political and social awareness. – Felgueiras Sérgio. Geração á Rasca . Chiado Books , 2017

The theme “urban violence” appears, therefore, as an interdisciplinary study proposal, in a nucleus integrated by several areas of social sciences (Sociology, Pedagogy, Philosophy, Anthropology, Economics, Psychology, Communication, Law, History and other related areas), with the purpose of understanding, through research and scientific work, the various aspects of urban violence, and directing socio-ideological changes that will guide public policies aimed at the causes and consequences of violence in this environment.

Contexts of violence

The hyper concentration of metropolises, over information and communication and information technologies in the centres of power and economic life, hyper-specialization and the increase in job insecurity produce an increasing number of excluded people who are left on the fringes of the labour market.

Employment and social and informational inclusion, exposed and vulnerable to unconventional, marginal, anomic and criminal forms of survival.

There is a culture of violence associated with large urban centres, with a high population density, due to social inequality, poverty and poor living conditions, marginality, the disruption of institutions such as the family, migrations of populations and ethnic groups, violent alternative cultures, etc.

Urban violence, violence associated with terrorism, armed conflicts, natural disasters, new epidemics, the effects of pollution, the greenhouse effect, illegal markets that proliferate with globalization, trafficking and organized crime, trade blood and organs, the precariousness of jobs, the financial situation of individuals, the difficulty of housing, the precariousness of retirement pensions, the new risks with food, create situations of violence and conflicts.

To contain the psychological and moral consequences of these phenomena, institutions and countries try to preserve democratic values, and NGOs (non-

governmental organizations) practice and spread the values of solidarity and fraternity, creating new forms of citizenship.

Citizenship

In the democratic rule of law, citizens must be guaranteed equal living conditions and fundamental rights of participation. Citizenship, in addition to requiring the training of citizens in the democratic public space, endowed with rights and duties, presupposes adherence to ethical principles in the name of which the values of democracy, participation and freedom are defended.

The lived space, of everyday life, functions as a cultural matrix of a common territory and, therefore, the framework par excellence of those of civic and community participation.

Against the background of logic of local development, we can say that civic participation, in the framework of this process, is a determining mechanism for the autonomy of populations, particularly those excluded, not in a perspective of isolation, but of an awareness of relations with the environment and the complexity of the problems, both at micro and macro levels.

This mechanism must be interactive, requiring, therefore, a voluntary effort on the part of the populations themselves, namely those that are most likely to intervene through their resources in terms of knowledge and their generational posture, we are referring to the young adults who attend higher education institutions.

Citizenship is a dynamic social construction that refers to a set of rights and duties that a member of a community or society has and in order to fully exercise it, it is necessary to consider empowerment as an approach that places populations in centre and core of development processes and a process through which social actors become aware of their competences and assume the destiny of their own trajectories.

All social actors are increasingly thirsty for the quality of places. It is necessary to bear in mind that the notion of quality of life is imbued with some relativity; we certainly do not find a universal definition and consensus in this regard.

However, living in society should provide the citizen with some conditions of access to a minimum threshold of quality of life, in terms of living conditions, in terms of access to a quality landscape and environment, access to social protection, employment, culture, leisure, health, social facilities, and civic participation. Thus, the exercise of active citizenship can enhance a quality experience, being an indispensable condition for its implementation.

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Aspects of urban violence in the context of the third millennium, every resident of the city are approached by violence.

This separates men, but at the same time unites them in the fear that inspires them. Cities, which were once synonymous with civilization, are now perceived as a segregated and decivilized fragmented environment.

According to Pedrazzini (2006), the territorial divisions and urbanism of oppression, which urban societies establish to confront them, update new techniques of barbarian invasions that must spring from the interior of the city.

Low wages and unemployment, which cause the impoverishment of the middle class and the increase in the number of poor people (pockets of poverty), have generated much of the crimes against property, such as theft, robbery and theft.

Residents, according to their intuitive understanding of the “reality of things”, got used to its changing character (common sense) and its necessary identification with these changes; without seeking to understand - in a critical way - to theorize and resist, they appropriate them within logic of chaos.

This happens, according to Pedrazzini (2006), because the residents first of all need to live. The chaotic state of urban space does not suit them or contribute to their activities, whether formal or informal.

The first to understand that no one would take care of their misfortune were the poorest. Violence is often located outside their daily activities and, at other times, it becomes the means of survival for those people.

Urban violence, for Pedrazzini (2006, p. 91), must be analyzed as part of a dynamic socio-spatial system whose structural elements would be the globalized liberal economy and the city as a hegemonic environmental model.

Faced with these two founding elements of our “civilization”, other components specifically social (growth of inequalities), political (crime of poverty), spatial

(fragmentation of territory) or ideological (subjection of democracy to security), which combine between themselves to outline a wild and unsettling society project.

For the aforementioned author, it is important to analyze how the main sectors of the globalized economy establish a certain model of urbanism, architecture and “global cities”, and, since then, how contemporary globalized urbanization began to impose social and spatial practices that contributed for the growth of urban violence (PEDRAZZINI, 2006).

The contemporary city is dangerous, as globalization divides it into antagonistic fragments, transforming it into a conflict of forces and interests. Since the 1980s of the twentieth century, the macroeconomic stabilization and structural adjustment programs imposed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank on developing countries so that their debts could be renegotiated have led hundreds of millions of people to impoverishment. Programs like the “European Financial Stabilisation Mechanism — EFSM” have largely contributed to destabilizing national currencies and ruining the economies of developing countries.

On the other hand, there was an increase in consumption in the high-income segment, which involves consumer durables and other luxury goods, which can only be reached by a small segment of the population.

This decomposition / re-composition of the economy of indebted countries and its insertion in the globalized economy, based on cheap labour, caused the compression of domestic demand and living standards - poverty, low wages and an abundant cheap labour - with reflexes in the continuous explosion of urban violence.

The violence of the poor conceals the violence of Globalization and the strategic fragmentation imposed on cities. Before, however, formulating any “preconceptions” about urban conflicts, it is up to us to identify the inhabitants of territories dominated by violence, as they are the undisputed holders of the answers about these conflicts.

It is necessary to go to the poor neighbourhood to question the people who live there and seek fruitful answers to the relationship of violence, the relationship with others, the strangeness of their neighbours and the terrifying acts.

The areas most affected by the tensions of globalization are evidently the poorest neighbourhoods in cities, as they are more exposed to the negative effects of globalized liberal politics.

Government officials are largely responsible for this situation, as they no longer offer residents real protection against the effects of because they no longer offer residents real protection against the effects of this evil.

The new generation

The new generation of young people from the slums of cities is a problem for the authorities and the police.

Certainly, violence is an immediate and often comfortable response to a constantly changing universe. Television media, radio stations, billboards, store windows, show products that represent standards of comfort, well-being and status.

You work, you struggle to get possession of these objects that seem to make people happy, rich and important. Happiness, therefore, is conditional on the possession of these material goods.

It is observed that the phenomenon of urban violence is constituted by a series of conflicting and increasingly complex situations, as well as uncontrollable, both by public authorities and by specialists in the private sector. In this context of globalized society, there is a weakening of the traditional defences of the social system, with values of solidarity and community ties, which are relativized by the individualistic sociability of the contemporary world.

Due to the complexity of the causes of urban violence within the alarming domain of economic and cultural globalization, there is a need to research it within an interdisciplinary context, in order to have scientific knowledge with results that can direct effective public policies to reduce urban violence and its effects on citizens.

Profit from insecurity

Violence in cities has scared and isolated its inhabitants in their own homes, which are becoming true fortresses. In large, medium-sized, or even small cities, it is not necessary to go very far to observe the large number of houses with electric fences, doors and windows with protection bars or even with signs identifying private security companies. What they monitor some residences twenty-four hours a day, preventing these houses from being invaded by people who chose the life of crime as a way of survival in the social dynamic.

Many people even take care to equip themselves with everything that modern technology offers in terms of food, information, communication and leisure, avoiding as much as possible leaving home.

In this condition, they enjoy the weekends between DVDs, plasma televisions, "telepizza", bathrooms with hydromassages, electronic games, hours on cell phones, etc.

Those who do not have access to this type of expensive and expensive solution, TV programming remains. People who risk leaving home at certain times are those who have almost nothing to offer criminals.

However, those who have something of value leave at pre-established times and visit places and spaces where greater security is offered, public or private.

Private security companies

The expansion of private security companies that sell their services, which range from monitored electric fences to private security guards, is a reality in the most varied cities.

These companies grow and people who can afford the cost of their services do not bother to pay for them, to feel more secure inside their homes or to leave them for their daily chores. We also noticed the huge demand for metalworkers that manufacture solid iron gates and gates that give the least protection to people with the lowest income when they are inside their homes.

At another end of the social sphere, in the peripheral neighbourhoods, where poverty is explicitly shown, the people who live there and live off the sweat of their work, in order to have a minimum of security, use shards and glass bottle ends stuck with pasta of cement on the walls, preventing their houses from being invaded by criminals who live in their midst.

In city centres, standardized cars from private security companies pass through the streets, and at night, they stay at strategic points, ready for the first warning signal from the monitoring centre.

We realize that the "Base Point" of public security - prevention - is gradually being replaced and administered by private companies, which, in the absence of serious public policies focused on security, are gaining ground. In the streets, hurried people grab their briefcases and bags.

They no longer stop to give some information, or, when they answer, they do so with an attentive eye to the movements of those who ask and attentive to the people passing by around them. People also no longer walk around to get to know and "enjoy" the city.

Thus, most contemporary cities and metropolises appear as a factory of fear, which favours the project of social division, giving certain actors the power to orient themselves, to define certain objectives and the means to achieve them within a capitalist social order.

Pollution, violence, poverty, hunger, as well as the “miracles” of the media, the plurality of cultures, ethnicities and traditions, the increase of creators, inventors and makers of history, are some of the pains and joys that metropolises and cities can offer or take back from their inhabitants.

The inhabitants create defence strategies against their own ghosts. These tactical strategies vary considerably, as we saw earlier, depending on the neighbourhood of the residence, the cultural level, the way of life and the profession.

The tendency, as stated in previous paragraphs, to privatize the means of security by increasing the apparatus of private security guards and private companies that offer this service to homeowners, whether rich or poor, is moving towards segregation urban space, where the success of urban architecture becomes a model of “police or militarized” architecture, which also expresses the search for profit due to insecurity in cities.

Public and private initiatives that aim to offer security to citizens raise only a cloistered civilization. Contemporary urbanism, in Pedrazzini's view (2006), is generally a police activity, according to the model implemented by Hausmann in Paris, in the 19th century, which aimed at better control of public spaces.

For this author, if current (contemporary) urbanism favours security, this architecture is dissuasive and military (architecture of relatively disguised fortifications in urban landscapes and a military occupation of urban land).

Given this, we witness the triumph of fear and the trivialization of fear urbanism. Not only have the most favoured classes submitted the urban space to privatization for security reasons.

However, the price to be paid for reinforcing the barriers built between the universe of prosperity and precariousness is not the same for all people. Iron gates and railings, broken glass and bottles have very reasonable costs compared to contracts by security companies for 24-hour monitoring of homes and businesses. In this growing context of segregation, property privileges give way to access privileges.

Security has become a service and an access that are offered as luxury items to customers of the most privileged sections of the population.

Contemporary urbanism, still in the view of the aforementioned author, presupposes the spread of the feeling of insecurity.

However, security projects designed to protect the set of city dwellers unequally favour their access to “safe” locations. Thus, for this author, the urbanism of fear causes a dramatic radicalization of the processes of spatial segregation, leading to a

classic urban fragmentation, in addition to a new planned fragmentation of the “Territories”, taking into account the degree of security or danger.

This selection can be observed in the reheating of the real estate market, especially in central areas, which, when they pass through a period of almost state and real estate abandonment, are reborn for urban requalification projects (PEDRAZZINI, 2006, p. 121).

The emergence of a security urbanism, however, does not bring improvements to the security of the cities or region in question.

It only establishes a duality in security practices, as responses to the duality of fear and violence of the rich and the poor, who listen, imitate or oppose, on each side, the economic iron curtain.

By combining the urbanism of fear and the holding of power in the hands of a few, in addition to the combination with the urbanism of urgency and the precariousness of life for many, the security measures created in this context are increasingly modelling a means segregated.

Security becomes the fetish for conjuring up evil and presents itself as the origin of the construction of new social inequalities in the urban context.

On the other hand, when we take into account that the world market for the defence against “terrorism” is valued at 100 billion Euros, and that for the security of information networks at 50 billion.

Conclusion

CEPEN - Centre for the Study of National Policies and Strategies, of which the author is a part, will launch a project for the Prevention of violence a strand of citizenship.

Justification of the Project

The consideration that all citizens have the right to security and the duty to create social and public conditions for citizenship and security encourages us to approach and analyze the phenomena of violence and conflict, in order to promote training actions in the fields security, civic behaviour and the prevention of violence and risks.

Such purpose requires an understanding of these phenomena with the aim of providing, in terms of training, the development of risk prevention skills, of responding to them and of security and citizenship conducts in different contexts.

With the objective of promoting in Higher Education Institutions personal and collective training in terms of values, knowledge, skills and competences for civic action, the project presented here is based on the ethical and legal principles of the

rule of law, the democratic and citizenship values, human rights, multiculturalism, aiming at understanding the phenomena of violence and the problem of security, in order to face ways of favouring security and trust and knowing how to respond adequately to situations of social and moral violence and conflict.

In short, it proposes to approach and deal with themes and problems related to violence, conflicts and security, with a view to advanced training for citizenship and civic practices that involves the debate and transmission of knowledge in these specific areas.

Guiding principles of the project

The guiding principles that govern this project are based on the consideration of interpersonal and social values, with particular attention to the autonomy and security of the individual, justice, responsibility and citizenship, in short, human rights and social peace.

Hence the purpose of training and guidance that promote the development of individual, interpersonal and social skills of active citizenship, but also the attention to consider the variety of perspectives of analysis of the referred phenomena, given the scope, complexity and even transversal of the themes and issues under study.

Depending on the purpose and principles stated, the following guidelines are proposed: Addressing in a logic of multidisciplinary and transversal of knowledge, issues that require the contributions of sociology, political science, clinical and social psychology, law and science of communication; Identify issues, delimit problems, point out guidelines and evaluate proposals; Build a global view of national specificities and problems in the area of security and violence prevention as a precondition for the full exercise of Citizenship.

Objectives

In terms of general objectives, it is intended to enable university students with tools for analysis, understanding and intervention in situations of violence and crisis, as well as providing them with reflective skills and citizenship practices; Explain concepts and apply them, updating them in an innovative perspective; Create synergies for the exchange of knowledge and knowledge, actions and modes of intervention with a view to safety and civility in public life.

In terms of specific objectives, the aim is to promote an understanding of the importance of the value of relationships with others, adherence to social values and norms and the use of rules of coexistence in different groups and social environments. Increase the capacity for understanding, intervention and resolution of conflict situations in a non-violent way. Develop the ability to identify risky behaviours and

encourage preventive attitudes. Promote skills to act appropriately in the face of aggression. Develop a culture of safety and enable self-protection.

Rationale

Three strategic axes of approach are considered: security, violence and citizenship, around which the themes to be addressed in the training sessions will be developed.

Safety

Security is an aspiration and an inalienable right of man. The understanding of security makes it possible to discern other correlative notions such as trust (Giddens) protection in the face of obstacles, threats or actions contrary to the person, institutions or essential goods. In modern societies, the development of the legal, health, education, engineering, economic, etc. systems has created areas of security, understood as "security in the credibility of a person or in the reliability of a system in certain circumstances" (Giddens, 2002: 24).

Trust, based on security, is the attitude that corresponds to an adherence or belief in people, abstract systems or institutions - the judge, the law, the courts are trusted, for example, based on experience.

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